

Advertisement of a vacancy.

Willful ignorance of concerns expressed in my letter of 13.03.2017 {1} and other symptoms of schizophrenia, by which Francis Collins is obviously affected {2–4}, make he incapable of fulfilling his obligations. In recognition of these facts, I release him from the position of the director of the U.S. National Institutes of Health, and announce a competition for appointment.

All persons qualified for announced position should send me their letters of interest electronically or to following address:

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Charitéplatz 1
10117 Berlin
Germany

References.

1. Letter of 13.03.2017 addressed to Dr. Francis S. Collins. In: A. Poleev. Letters to the american people. Enzymes, 2018. <http://enzymes.at/download/letters.pdf>
2. The accusation of Springer. In: A. Poleev. Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis. Enzymes, 2019. <http://enzymes.at/download/ppe.pdf>
3. Desacralization of Vatican. <http://enzymes.at/judgments/Vatican.pdf>
4. A. Poleev. German disease. Enzymes, 2019. <http://enzymes.at/download/Schizophrenie.pdf>